

Big Data with NoSQL Databases to overcome drawbacks of Relational Databases

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Abstract - NoSQL databases, like relational databases, offer their own set of advantages and disadvantages. It's crucial to remember that "the appropriate tool for the right job" is a valuable idea while the NoSQL revolution proceeds. Non-relational databases support research while relational databases support accuracy and redundancy.

Keywords - Relational database, NoSQL, SQL, Big data

I. INTRODUCTION

Prior to the discovery of internet, cloud architecture, big data, mobile, and today's vastly interactive enterprises, relational DBMS (database management systems) had been developed in an age of mainframe computers and business applications. These databases were meant to operate on a single dedicated server, and the larger the server, the better. The only option to increase the capacity of these databases was to scale up the servers, which meant upgrading the CPUs, memory, and storage. Enterprises must innovate to be competitive in today's experience-driven digital economy – and they must provide it faster than ever before. Developers must produce apps and services rapidly since this focus of this advancement is on the creation of new web, mobile, and IoT applications. Because modern applications change at a fast-moving rate compared to legacy applications like ERP, speed and agility are essential characteristics.

II. BIG DATA

Big data is an emerging technology that deals in massive amounts of data (as in terabytes to zettabytes) that is interpreted differently. However, the three V's, volume, variety, and velocity, are adequate to illustrate the most general properties of big data [5]

The three properties of big data are depicted in Figure 1.[6]

- Volume: Size of the data.
- Variety: Data that comes from a variety of sources.

- Velocity: Data that is broadcast in real time.

Figure 1 Big Data 3V's

III. RELATIONAL DATABASE

A relational database is a collection of data which has described relationships and are easily accessible. In the relational database paradigm, data structures such as data tables, indexes, and views are stored separately from physical storage structures, allowing database managers to update the physical data storage without affecting the logical data structure.

The relational Database model was presented in the 1960s and "it's the model that deals with data and organizes it into one or more tables, or we could call it a relation, which consists of columns and rows, defining that relation with a unique key"[1][2]

Relational databases comprise of several advantages such as, [4]

- ACID (Availability, Consistency, Isolation, and Durability) properties
- Strong consistency, concurrency, and recovery.
- Context through arithmetic
- SQL
- Vertical scaling (up scaling)

However, Relational databases have several disadvantages, such as the inability to handle large amounts of data and distributed databases that contain a wide range of data types and due to their inflexible data model following drawbacks are existed [10].

- Relational databases scale out vertically but not horizontally (concurrency and data size) (except for sharding).

- Using joins means data is normalized, which bogs down the speed.
- Working with semi-structured data is a challenge.

IV. NOSQL DATABASE

SQL systems are commonly used to refer to relational databases. The word NoSQL can refer to either "No SQL systems" or "Not exclusively SQL," to underline those certain systems may offer SQL-like query languages. [7]

NoSQL databases debuted as expenses dropped significantly in the late 2000s. Times when attempting to avoid redundant data required the development of a complex, difficult-to-manage data model. Since developers (instead of storage) have become the main expense of software development, NoSQL databases have been intended to optimize throughput. [8]

As expenses for storage dropped, so did the quantity of data which programs needed to store and query. Such data came in a variety of formats – structured, semi-structured, and polymorphic – causing it almost impossible to describe its schema in advance. NoSQL databases provide devs with a great deal of flexibility whilst also letting them to hold huge volumes of unstructured data.

NoSQL is a "class of database management systems (DBMS)" that stands for "Not Only SQL" and has the following characteristics: [3][9]

- There is no set schema (schema less)
- There are no joins (as is common in SQL databases).
- Distributed, partition-tolerant design
- Does not employ SQL as a querying language

NoSQL systems follow CAP (consistency ,availability,partition tolerance) theorem which mention NoSQL can achieve only two of characteristics from CAP therefore almost all NoSQL systems do not satisfy ACID compliance and BASE (Basically Available, Soft-state, eventually consistent) compliance.[13]

NoSQL Data Model are categorized into four main types.[13]

- Key-Value databases - These are the simplest NoSQL data stores to utilize in terms of API. Redis and Riak are the most popular.
- Document databases - which store and retrieve documents in various formats such as XML, JSON, BSON, and others. MongoDB is the most popular document database, with a powerful query language.

- Column family stores - this model store data in column families, which are rows with many columns linked by a row key. Cassandra is one of the most well-known.

- Graph Databases - These databases allow users to store entities as well as the relationships between them. There are several graph databases available, but OrientDB, FlockDB, neo4j are popular databases.

V. NOSQL VS SQL DATABASE IN BIG DATA ANALYTICS

Times over the past three decades, relational databases have been the easiest option for data model deployment in businesses across the globe, using SQL as the syntax programmed to deliver basic data processes. Relational databases are widely being used and come with many advantages. [8]

- Structured data is handled.
- ACID properties and "joins" are supported.
- A big eco-system and built-in data integrity.
- Relationships are constrained.
- Indexing is unrestricted.
- Strong SQL.

Nevertheless, because data size had already continued to increase, SQL-based data querying is becoming less effective, so managing significantly bigger datasets has now become a serious hurdle.

The primary cause to shift from relational database systems to NoSQL is to enhance efficiency. Choi et al [15] discovered using a NoSQL database like MongoDB supplied quite secure as well as speedier value in terms of data consistency.

The studies were conducted out on an internal blog system which was constructed on an open-source project. MongoDB was discovered to be 850 percent faster than a SQL database at storing posts. These have been recommended that NoSQL are used in contexts under which availability of data is more important than consistency.[14]

Due to the general big memory space being used by NoSQL database, it was discovered this was slower than the relational database. Having read a massive amount of data taxes the database, and because of the unstructured format of NoSQL databases, storing thousands of records necessitates a sizable space for storage, whereas RDBMS requires less storage.

CONCLUSION

By summarizing what we have discussed so far, NoSQL database can be used when,

- Bringing in fresh data that is large and/or diverse.
- The data is semi-structured and non-relational.

The capacity to handle enormous amounts of user requests, a plus point of non-relational databases, is the significant feature for web-based applications. Consider when users can explore and view posted things on eBay. A fraction of this percentage of customers would make an actual offer or request a product, majority of individuals will view millions, if not billions, of sites daily. Apart from implementing stringent business regulations, eBay is more concerned with a quick reaction time and ensuring fast website loading.

Because Big Data has necessitated the development of next-generation data analytics tools [16][17], it is reasonable to expect SQL and NoSQL databases to collaborate. High speed data processing is required in cloud facilitating SQL databases to enable efficient elasticity [18] and Big Data analytics which include contemporary and historical data as well as forecasting.

Modern cloud monitoring solutions are now being suggested, with the use of NoSQL databases as the backend to accomplish extremely quick responses.

REFERENCES

- [1] Raj, P., &Deka, G. "A Deep Dive into NoSQL Databases". San Diego: Elsevier Science &Technology., 2018.
- [2] M. State, "Relational Database Management Systems Semester - III," Management, no. 9038, pp. 1–8.
- [3] Radoev, M. (2017). "A Comparison between Characteristics of NoSQL Databases and Traditional Databases". Computer Science And Information Technology, 5(5), 149-153. doi: 10.13189/csit.2017.050501]:
- [4] M. A. Mohamed and O. G. Altrafi, "Relational vs .NoSQL Databases : A Survey," vol. 03, no. 03, pp. 598–601, 2014.
- [5] A. Corbellini, C. Mateos, A. Zunino, D. Godoy and S. Schiaffino. "Persisting Big Data: The NoSQL landscape". Information Systems. Vol. 63, pp. 1-23. Elsevier Science, 2017.
- [6] A. E. YOUNESS KHOURDIFI, MOHAMED BAHAI, "A new approach for migration of a relational Database into column-oriented A NEW APPROACH FOR MIGRATION OF A RELATIONAL DATABASE INTO COLUMN-ORIENTED NOSQL DATABASE ON HADOOP," no. November, 2018.
- [7] Raj, P., &Deka, G. "A Deep Dive into NoSQL Databases". San Diego: Elsevier Science &Technology., 2018
- [8] N. D. Karande, "A Survey Paper on NoSQL Databases : Key-Value Data Stores and Document Stores," vol. 6, no. 2, pp. 153–157, 2018.
- [9] H. Vyawahare, "NoSql Database," no. June, 2017.
- [10] N. C. Ug and J. Steemann, "Column-oriented databases," pp. 1–34, 2012
- [11] M. Stonebraker, "SQL databases v. NoSQL databases," Commun.ACM Journal, vol. 53, no. 10–12, 2010.
- [12] K. Sahatqija, J. Ajdari, X. Zenuni, B. Raufi, and F. Ismaili, "Comparison between relational and NOSQL databases," no. May, 2018.]
- [13]A. Moniruzzaman and S. Hossain, "NoSQL Database: New Era of Databases for Big data Analytics - Classification, Characteristics and Comparison", International Journal of Database Theory and Application, vol. 6, pp. 3-10, 2013
- [14] Ullah, Md A. (2015), „A Digital Library for Plant Information with Performance Comparison between a Relational Database and a NoSQL Database (RDF Triple Store)", Technical Library, Paper 205.
- [15] Choi, Y., Jeon, W., & Yo, S. (2014), 'Improving Database System Performance by Applying NoSQL', Journal Of Information Processing Systems, 10(3), 355-364.
- [16] Warden P. (2012), Big Data Glossary - A Guide to the New Generation of Data Tools, O'Reilly, USA.
- [17] Zareian S., Fokaefs, M., Khazaei H. Litoiu M. & Zhang X. (2016), 'A Big Data Framework for Cloud Monitoring', Proceedings of the 2nd International Workshop on BIG Data Software Engineering (BIGDSE'16), ACM Digital Library, 58-64.
- [18] Ramanathan, V. & Venkatraman, S. (2015), Cloud Adoption in Enterprises: Security Issues and Strategies, 96-121, Book Chapter In Haider A. and Pishdad A. (Eds.), Business Technologies in Contemporary Organizations: Adoption, Assimilation, and Institutionalization, IGI Global Publishers, USA.